

A REVIEW OF RENEWABLE ENERGY ACTIVITIES IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

This paper reviews foretell of accessible renewable energy recourses and its activities up to December 2017 with combine renewable energy sources and its potentials in viewpoint in Bangladesh. This paper also reviews the contribution of private and public sector and its future planning in Bangladesh. Among several renewable energy resources, the application of solar photovoltaic (PV) is renowned and adaptation of CSP technology, another part of solar energy can brings a solution of future sustainable-economical source of power. Additionally, wind, biogas, mini hydro and tidal are also well known. A plan has been initiated by the government of Bangladesh (GOB) to generate 5% of the total energy from renewable energy resources within 2015 and 10% by the year of 2020. Through the approved renewable energy policy, the GOB is devoted to make possible investment in renewable energy projects to substitute simultaneous non-renewable energy resources and escalate the contributions of renewable energy based electricity generation. With this context, review of recent activities on concurrent renewable energy resources is imperative as well as to explore potentials of resources. After reading this paper, an investor will get momentous information about present scenario and steering for future participation of renewable energy sources in Bangladesh.

Key words: Renewable energy, Solar PV, Concentrating solar power (CSP), Solar park, Solar rooftop, and Geothermal energy.

Introduction

Bangladesh is a sub-tropical country. The line of cancer is in the middle of Bangladesh. Geographically Bangladesh is situated in the north-eastern of south Asia between 20.84°& 26.838° North Latitude and 88.801°& 92.841° East Latitude. The total population is about 166,021,529 with an average population density near about 1278 per sq. km which is highest in the world². 64% of the population live in the rural areas of Bangladesh is seriously dispossessed of the access to electricity. As because the expansion of grid is inordinately expensive in the rural areas; already initiatives have been taken to popularize the use of renewable energy sources. The prospect, development, consumption and its technology as well as reviews of the policy, institutions and opportunities based on renewable energy technology towards sustainable development and climate change mitigation has been investigated in paper. This paper also investigates how we overcome when the conventional energy sources like gas is shortage and we can use renewable sources as alternative. An up to date scenario of the renewable energy allied activities in Bangladesh is offered in this paper.

In Bangladesh, the per capita energy consumption is one of the lowest in the region. On an average in Bangladesh per capita energy consumption is 433 kwh³ compared to 1434 kwh in India, 1380 kwh in Pakistan, 920 kwh in Nepal and 1270 kwh in Sri Lanka. The average energy consumption in Asia is 1732kWh (*Mehedi Hasan et al. 2017*). Due to nonstop failure of power, development and welfare of

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² www.worldometers.info/world-population/bangladesh-population, accessed on 19.04.2018

³ Annual report 2016-2017, BPDB, accessed on 19.04.2018

the citizens have been uncomfortable, so the government is forced to move into contractual agreements at high costs and adopt convenient solutions of purchasing rental power and small IPP on an emergency based on diesel or liquid fuel. Due to gas shortage and inadequate new generation addition in the few years back, demand of electricity outpaced generation capacity caused persistent load shedding. The use of renewable energy is a solution of this crisis. The strategy has created equilibrium approach regarding both supply increase and demand management aspects of the energy market. Specifically the strategy would try to determine what can be done by the government about gas and power and to explore for a variety of options to diversify the fuels for power generation.

Energy demand and generation capacity and future projects

In Bangladesh, installed generation capability (December 2017) has reached to 16046MW and the maximum generation is 10084MW where the maximum demand is 12000 MW⁴. Nearly 65% of total generation is obtained from natural gas besides the renewable part of the generation which comes from hydro and some solar PV power plant which is around 2.87%⁵. In contrast, around 4.8 million IDCOLs SHS program has installed solar home system. Their goal is to finance 6 million SHSs by the end of the year of 2018.

Review of various renewable energy activities in Bangladesh

1. Solar PV application in Bangladesh

The application of solar PV especially SHS program is mainly found in remote areas of Bangladesh. Additionally, hybrid micro grid with solar PV, solar PV based irrigation system, grid-tied solar PV systems are also in operation. These are described below.

1.1 Solar Home System

In Bangladesh, access to energy for services like cooling and lighting in off-grid villages is slender. Most rural households have to rely on kerosene lamps for lighting and traditional stoves for cooking. The government has initiated a variety of programs and has given massive efforts to establish flexibility in rural economy. Solar power, especially SHS technology, has been welcomed by the rural people as a reasonable way to fulfill requirement of lighting. As a result, IDCOL started the SHS program in January 2003 to fulfill basic electricity requirement of the off-grid rural people of Bangladesh as well as supplement the government's vision of ensuring access to electricity for all citizen of Bangladesh by 2021. Up to December 2017, in the off-grid rural areas of Bangladesh more than 4.8 million SHSs have already been installed under the supervision of the program where electrification through grid expansion is challenging and costly. Thus the program has ensured supply of solar electricity to 20 million people i.e. 12% of the country's total population who previously used kerosene lamps for lighting purpose. IDCOL has a target to finance 6 million SHS by 2021 with an estimated generation capacity of 230 MW of electricity. IDCOL initially received credit and grant support from the World Bank and GEF to start the program. Later, GIZ, KfW, ADB, IDB, GPOBA, JICA, USAID and DFID came ahead with supplementary financial support for extension of the SHS Program. IDCOL's total investment under the program is BDT 52,240 million (USD 696 million) out of which loan USD 600 million and grant USD 96 million. The program has so far saved consumption of 1.14 million tons of kerosene worth USD 411 million approx. In addition, in the next 15 years already installed 4.8 million SHS will save consumption of another 3.7 million tons of kerosene worth USD 1,360 million. Moreover, around 75,000 people are directly or indirectly involved with the program. The program has been acclaimed as the largest off-grid renewable energy program in the world. Many mobile phone operators have decided to run off-grid BTSs with solar diesel hybrid power systems for continuous voice and data services. As the primary power source these systems use solar PV and as backup diesel generator. In the telecom sector so far IDCOL has financed 178 such solar-diesel hybrid power solutions⁶.

⁴ www.bpdb.gov.bd, accessed on 19.04.2018

⁵ Annual report 2016-2017, BPDB, accessed on 19.04.2018

⁶ www.idcol.org/, accessed on 19.04.2018

1.1.1 The present situation of the world largest off-grid renewable energy program

The present situation of the world largest off-grid renewable energy program SHSs is not good. According to annual report 2016 of IDCOL, Interest income from Renewable Energy project loan has overall declined by 5% mainly because of decline in the sale of SHSs. The declines in sales have been persistent from 2014, due to market saturation and uneven competition from the market where poor quality SHSs are offered at a lower price. In addition to this, in 2015, government initiated a safety net program (KABIKHA/TR program) distributing free SHS throughout the country causing serious setback on IDCOL SHS program. IDCOL's net profit after tax in FY 2016 stands to BDT 397.9 million that is 71 % lower than BDT1, 366.14 million last year⁷.

1.2 Solar PV based irrigation system

Bangladesh has 14.76 million hectares of total land in which 8.3 million hectares are net cultivable and 7.56 million hectares are irrigable. Besides this, irrigation pump has been well thought-out as a major invention to ensure food security. There are about 1.42 million diesel based irrigation pumps are operating in the country, therefore requiring about 1 million ton of diesel per year⁸. Solar powered irrigation system is a pioneering, economic and environment friendly solution for the agro-based economy of Bangladesh. Average capacity of each solar pump will be 8kWp with a head of 12-15 meters. Area coverage will be on an average 13 hector of paddy fields by a single pump. It is estimated that 18,700 diesel-based irrigation pumps will be replaced by solar powered pumps under this program. Total solar power capacity in this case will be 150 MW, which will reduce 95,000 liters of diesel and momentous amount of CO₂ emission per day. IDCOL has approved 629 solar irrigation pumps of which 607 are already in operation. The remaining pumps are expected to come into operation shortly. IDCOL has a target to finance 1500 solar irrigation pumps by 2018.

1.3 Solar PV based micro-grid

Many regions in Bangladesh which are underprivileged of consuming electricity from national grid depend on micro-grid to fulfill their electricity demand. Government has plan to install 50 Micro-grid based on solar PV by 2018. From this context, initially, 30 remote areas have been identified under this program where grid expansion is not planned for next 15-20 years. Additional new areas will be identified to develop solar mini grid system on the basis of successful implementation. Total solar power capacity in addition from this constituent will be 100 MW. Besides these, BPDB, REB has installed larger size of solar PV systems in various locations of Bangladesh. IDCOL has installed 100-kW solar photovoltaic (PV) based micro-grid by PUROBI Green Energy Limited (PGEL) at Sandwip island in Chittagong. To alleviate the problem of low solar radiation a 40-kW diesel generator has been incorporated into the suggested power plant in order to ensure adequate power supply⁹. BPDB has installed 650kWp solar mini grid project at Shalla, Sunamganj which is the largest solar mini grid project in south Asia. IDCOL aims to finance 50 solar mini-grid projects by 2018.

1.4 Large scale solar power plant

Bangladesh has recently been able to see its First Ever Solar Power Plant with a capacity of 3 MW. From 3rd August'17 this Large-scale Solar Power Plant started supplying power to the National Grid, which is for the first time in the country's history, evacuating power to the nearby BPDB-owned Jamalpur Sarishabari 33/11 kV Sub-station. This plant has used eight acres of land located at Shimla bazaar, Sarishabari of Jamalpur, under BOO arrangement with BPDB. The EPC (Engineering, Procurement & Construction) of this Power Plant was done by Engreen. This success story is obviously something for Bangladesh to cheer about and should be considered as a milestone for others to follow. The plant has started its journey by connecting to national grid experimentally on 15th July, 2017 and then commercially from 3rd August; 2017. The plant consists of total 11,530 nos.

⁷ IDCOL Annual report 2016-2017, accessed on 19.04.2018

⁸ www.badc.gov.bd, accessed on 19.04.2018

⁹ www.pgel.bd.com, accessed on 19.04.2018

of Solar PV Modules, with total installed DC capacity of 3.28 MWp. With the fixed 8 acres of land, the target was to maximize use of the land maintaining the Solar Generation Yield to the highest possible Unit. Engreen has made it possible through an optimized design along with the high efficient 285Wp German made Mono-crystalline Solar Panels having fewer footprints. From the date of its commission to mid-October'17, this solar plant has been able to feed around 8, 00,000 KWh of electricity to the national grid. Comparing with the conventional Diesel based Power Plant, it can be said that the plant has avoided burning of around 2, 00,000 Liters of Diesel within two and half-months of its operation. In other way, it can be said that the plant so far has been reduced an emission of 575 tons of Carbon dioxide (CO₂) equivalent. The plant is now supplying power to the PDB in the Sarishabari 33/11 KV sub-grid station area at per unit rate of 0.1897 US cents, equivalent to Tk14.74. The state-owned PDB will continue to buy power from the plant for the next 20 years¹⁰.

1.5 Solar Park

With an intention to reduce dependency on fossil fuel electricity generation Govt. has initiated the plan to set grid tied solar based power generation projects in the Govt. owned non-agricultural lands. Power generated from the solar park will be directly feed into the grid on commercial basis. The power generated from the Solar Park will directly be fed into the Grid on commercial basis. No Battery back-up will be used. Primarily 25 potential sites have been identified under two categories which total capacity is 1408MW. More exploration is underway.

Table 1: Under planning solar park list¹¹

S.N	Project Name	Capacity (MW)	Location	Completion date
1	100 MW (AC) Solar Park by Energon Technologies FZE, UAE & China SunergyCo.Ltd (ESUN)	100	Mongla, Bagerhat	30.06.2018
2	50 MW (AC) Solar Park by Consortium of Hanwha 63 City Co. Ltd., BJ Power Company Limited & Solar City Bangladesh Ltd.	50	Basail, Tangail	30.06.2018
3	100 MW (AC) Solar Park by Zhejiang Dun An New Energy Co., Ltd, China National Machinery Import & Export Corporation, Solar Tech Power Limited, & Amity Solar Limited	100	Aditmari, Lalmonirhat	30.06.2018
4	8 MW (AC) Solar Park by Parasol Energy Ltd. Installation of a 100 MWp Solar Photovoltaic (PV)	8	Tetulia, Panchagarh	30.06.2018
5	based Grid-connected Power Generation Plant, Sonagazi, Feni	100	Sonagazi, Feni	30.06.2019
6	Rangunia 60 MWp Solar Park Project Rangunia, Chittagong	60	Rangunia, Chittagong	30.06.2018
7	Gangachara 55 MWp Solar Park	55	Gangachara, Rangpur	30.06.2018
8	Faridpur Solar Park (Grid Tied)	100	Charbhadrasan, Faridpur	30.06.2018
9	Sirajganj Solar Park (Grid Tied)	7.60	Sadar, Sirajgonj	30.06.2018
10	Ashuganj 100 MW Grid Tied Solar Park	100	Katiadi, Kishoreganj	31.12.2020
11	Madargonj 100MW Solar PV Power Project	100	Madarganj, Jamalpur	30.06.2019
12	30 MW Solar Park	30	Boda, Panchagarh	30.06.2018
13	5 MW (AC) Solar Park by Sun Solar Power Plant Ltd.	5	Gowainghat, Sylhet	31.12.2019
14	50 MW Solar Park by 8minut energy Singapore Holdings 2 Pte. Ltd. Singapore	50	Sadar, Panchagarh	31.12.2019
15	100 MW Solar Park by ShapoorjiPallonji Infrastructure Capital Company Private Ltd.	100	Sadar, Pabna	31.08.2019

¹⁰ www.engreen.bd.com, accessed on 19.04.2018

¹¹ www.sreda.gov.bd, accessed on 19.04.2018

1.6 Rooftop solar

Bangladesh is a blessed with ample sunshine round the year and this can help satisfy industries ever increasing need for electricity and industrialists need to take a fresh look at their roofs. It requires only 100 Sq.ft. space and about Tk. 75,000 to generate 1.0 KW of electricity. The unit cost of electricity from rooftop solar falls below Tk. 8.0/unit and this is the opportunity the industrialists utilize. According to the Bangladesh Energy Regulatory Commission, the flat rate of electricity for industries is Tk. 8.20/unit and this is further subsidized by the government of Bangladesh (GOB). Furthermore, the rate is increasing every year and thus making the industrial production cost even higher. Often the industries do not rely solely on the grid connection because of power outage and instead use diesel generators. Use of diesel generators is expensive and harmful for the environment as it emits carbon into the atmosphere. It is estimated that the average cost of industrial electricity ranges between Tk.12-15/unit considering the electricity consumption from the national grid and the diesel generators. The GOB has set a target to generate 2000 MW of electricity from renewable energy by 2021, of which more than 1600 MW will be produced from solar energy. It is estimated that more than 400 MW of electricity can be produced from the textile industries rooftops and there is a potential of producing about 400 MW of electricity from industrial and commercial rooftops. IDCOL has 30 solar rooftop projects in the pipeline with a cumulative capacity of 30 MW and IDCOL intends to finance solar rooftop projects to generate 1000 MW¹².

2. Possibility of concentrating solar power (CSP) in Bangladesh

Bangladesh gets solar radiation of average 4-6.2KWh/m²/per day that shows a great prospect for all types of solar power generation technologies ranging from small to large scale. However, solar power technologies controlled in only Photovoltaic (PV) technology though it deserves ideal condition for concentrated solar power (CSP) technologies of power generation. CSP plants can recompense shortage and add to production of power moreover reduces carbon dioxide emissions. As survey of energy resources (SER) – 2004, world energy council, oxford, UK state that one long-term scenario foresees that by 2040 CSP's contribution would be at a level of almost 630000 MW (*Amit Barua et.al.2014*). From research it has been found that CSP plant with direct normal irradiance levels (DNI) of 2000 kWh/m²/year or more are economic in operations. Therefore, DNI more than 5 kWh/m²/day is required. Tracking the sun can provide a significantly greater energy yield for a given DNI. Globally CSP plants are installed and led by USA, Spain and their average DNI are 2700 kWh/m²/year and 2100 kWh/m²/year respectively. Similarly Bangladesh has convenient meteorological condition for efficient CSP plant operations along with many potential locations having annual DNI ranging from 1500 to 2300 kWh/m². About 180×10⁹ Mwhr/year electricity can be generated if solar radiation is 5kWh/m²/day and it is 105 times the energy presently generated as electricity (*Nafisa noor et.al.2014*). Necessary meteorological factors for CSP plants are given in Table.

Table 2: Meteorological factors of Bangladesh¹³

Latitude	20.30 - 26.38 degrees north and 88.04 - 92.44 degrees east
Average temperature	27 to 32 degrees
Average rainfall	2250 mm
Direct Normal irradiance (DNI)	4 to 6.5 kWh/m ² /day
Daily average of bright sunshine	7.55 Hours
Average shiny day	300 days

3. Other renewable energy sources

Other than the solar PV, there are some other renewable energy sources available in Bangladesh.

¹² The Financial Express, accessed on 18.03,2018

¹³ Bangladesh Meteorological Department, accessed on 19.04.2018

3.1 Biogas Energy

An agro-based country like Bangladesh has huge potential for utilizing biogas technologies. According to IFRD, Bangladesh has plenty of resources to establish four million biogas power plants. Till December 2017, IDCOL has financed construction of over 46,200 biogas plants all over the country. The program saves 44,300 tons of firewood every year worth USD 3.7 million and also reduces the use of 39,300 tons of chemical fertilizer worth USD 9.3 million by producing 274,000 tons of organic fertilizer. The program also reduces the use of 1,400 tons of kerosene every year. IDCOL has a plan to install 60,000 biogas plants in Bangladesh by 2018¹⁴.

3.2 Hydro energy

The exclusive hydropower plant in Bangladesh is the Karnafuli Hydro Power station located at kaptai about 50 km apart from Chittagong. Currently it has the capacity of 230 MW by 5 units. BPDB is appraising the operation and planning to increase its generation up to 330 MW. The Water Development Board (BWDB) and BPDB carried out a joint study on micro-hydro power potential in the country. With a view to install other two hydro power plants at the Sangu and Matamuhuri rivers two sites have been selected. The projects will be named as The Sangu Project and The Matamuhuri Project comprising the generation capability of 140 MW and 75 MW respectively. At Barkal Upazila of Rangamati district, a 50 kW micro-hydro plant was installed in 2005. The ongoing projects are: 50-70 kW Mohamaya Irrigation-cum-Hydro Power Project at Mirersorai, Chittagong. Rehabilitation of 50 kW micro-hydro power plants at Barkal Upazila of Rangamati district is completed.

3.3 Wind Energy

The annual average wind speed for a wind energy project should exceed 4 m/s at a height of 10 m above the ground. General Types of Wind Turbine are Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine (HAWT) and Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT)¹⁵. The prospective of wind energy is partial to offshore islands, coastal areas, rivers sides and other inland open areas with strong wind regime. BPDB installed 4 units of 225 KW which is accumulated to 900 KW capacity grid connected wind plant at Muhuri dam area of Sonagazi in Feni with a look forward to generate electricity from wind energy. In 2008, another project of 1000 KW wind-battery hybrid power plant at Kutubdia Island was proficient, which comprises of 50 wind turbines of 20 kW capacity each. Restoration of the accessible Kutubdia 1000 kW wind battery hybrid power project is complete. Steps have been taken to install 15 MW wind power plant cross ways the coastal regions of Bangladesh after a year of wind resources appraisal in Mognamaghat of Coxsbazar, Muhuri dam area of Feni, Parky beach of Anwara in Chittagong, Kuakata of Patuakhali and Kepupara of Borguna. Wind mapping is going on at Muhuri dam area of Feni and at Mognamaghat of Coxs-bazar by Regen Power tech Ltd. of India. Under the supervision of USAID TA project, installation of wind monitoring stations at Inani beach of Cox'sbazar, Parky Beach of Anwara, Sitakundu of Chittagong and at Chandpuris also underway.

3.4 Possibility of Ocean wave energy in Bangladesh

For the energy requirements of coastal nation's ocean energy can give a significant contribution, especially those with island communities if it converting into useable forms. In the coastal zone of Bangladesh, access of electricity is lower than 3% out of 10 million people and national grid will not come for many years in most of the islands, if at all. Bangladesh is a country vastly surrounded by water. Bangladesh has a wide coastal area and longest uninterrupted shoreline. It has a 724 km of coastal line along the Bay of Bengal. So Bangladesh harnesses a huge potential of wave energy that may be the vital source of electricity and can face the energy crisis problem of island communities in Bangladesh.

¹⁴ www.idcol.org/, accessed on 19.04.2018

¹⁵ www.engreen.bd.com, accessed on 19.04.2018

3.5 Possibility of Tidal Energy in Bangladesh

As tides are more predictable than wind and sunlight, tidal energy can easily be generated from the changing sea levels. The coastal area of Bangladesh has a tidal rise and fall of between 2 to 5 meters. Among these coastal areas, Sandwip has the best prospect because more than 5 meter tidal rise fall to generate tidal energy. By applying low and medium head tidal movements of height within 2-5 m from coastal tidal resources, Bangladesh can accomplish sufficient amount of tidal energy. Low head tidal movements are suitable in areas like Satkhira, Barisal, Khulna, Bagerhat and Cox's Bazar regions. In Sandwip, high tidal movement more than 5 meters of tidal wave is utilized to produce tidal energy. Accessibility of such tides can be a great source of electrical energy for Bangladesh.

3.6 Possibility of Geothermal energy in Bangladesh

In this region, the geothermal slope ranges from 22.8° to 50.7°C/km. Research conceded exhibited the possible of a geothermal resource in Thakurgaon district. Singra-Kuchma-Bogra is hopeful areas of scrutiny in the Bogra projection region; the Singra well with over 150°C bottom whole temperature is the most auspicious among the three areas. There are two special areas like the Madhyapara hard rock mine area and the Barapukuria coal basin area. Using geochemical information from water samples of the Madhyapara hard rock mine area's basement aquifer, temperature was found to be varying in the range of 67° to 153°C, referring to a feasible low-temperature geothermal reservoir in this area. In the southeast region, geothermal slope varies from 19.8° to 29.5°C/km. Sitakund hilly area is a place of curiosity because of having few thermal springs. Elsewhere Hatiya trough at Shahbajpur well has the highest slope of 29.5°C/km followed by Saldanadi with slope of 27.2°C/km in this region (Vivekananda Das et. al.2017).

Research for utilizing geothermal resources of Bangladesh has been largely constrained within few works carried out by geologists. In 2011, Anglo MGH Energy, a Dhaka based private company announced the construction of 200 MW geothermal plant, first ever of such kind, in Thakurgaon district. But for some unknown reasons, this project never commenced, and no development in this field has been announced afterwards.

Conclusion

For arising country like Bangladesh, practical and careful use of renewable resources is overriding. Representation electricity to all the classes of people can ensure a fortunate and more comfortable life. Renewable energy, especially solar PV is getting popular to mitigate energy crisis. Mini Grid along with SHS can be much more efficacious and considered as a better solution to have the power with prime quality, reliability and sustainability

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